

Current Issues of Registration of Intellectual Property

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Abstract:

This article highlights the essence of the digital economy, the importance of innovation. Special attention was paid to the problems and solutions of intellectual property, patent registration in the transformation of innovative development into digital.

Keywords: innovative development, digitization, digital economy, digital technology, information technology, intellectual property, patent.

Introduction

No one is immune to the fact that the revolution is changing the economy and society at an unprecedented rate, which in turn is creating huge opportunities and challenges. Currently, the growth rate of the "digital economy" in the world is almost 15.5%. In developed countries, the share of the "digital economy" in GDP has reached 7%. These countries have benefited greatly from the introduction of the "digital economy". In particular, the United States exports more than \$ 400 billion a year in "digital services." By 2025, the U.S. is expected to earn an additional \$ 20 trillion from the "digitization" of the industry.

At a new stage of development of Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the digitalization of public administration, the widespread use of digital technologies in all spheres and industries. For example: "we need to develop a national concept of Digital Economy, which envisages the renewal of all sectors of the economy in the context of digital technologies. In this regard, it is stated that "we need to implement the Digital Uzbekistan-2030".

[1]. The successful realization of this category depends, first of all, on the national inconvenient capital - the fact that our kindergarten has a deep modern knowledge and a high level of mahogany.

Also, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-5349 of February 18, 2018 "On measures to further improve the field of information technology and communications", PQ-3832-con of July 3, 2018 "On measures to develop the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan", PQ-3927-con of September 2, 2018 "On the establishment of the Fund for Support of Digital Economy" "Digital Trust", Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 20, 2019 No. 421 On Additional Measures to Improve the Procedure for Providing Services "and other normative and legal acts aimed at stimulating and accelerating the transition to a digital economy in the country.

In Japan, economic and mathematical modeling, social psychology, information, and telecommunication technologies, as well as science and technology, have shaped the formation of the economy. In other words, it has paved the way for the emergence of advanced technologies for data acquisition, transmission, processing, and storage.

Literature review.

Today, there is a radical interpretation of the concept of "smart economy". For example, economic activity based on e-commerce technology; a system of economic, social, and cultural communication based on the use of intelligent economy-information-communication technologies, as well as intelligent economic-information-communication technologies.

The digital economy is a science that studies the economic activities of the economy, which involves the development, distribution, and consumption of social goods in Japan. First of all, a rational economy is a modern stage of development, which is characterized by creative work and the success of the media. Secondly, the digital economy is a special theory, which its object is informed society.

In a step-by-step economy, the gradual transition to such an economic system is the key element of production in the socio-economic sphere.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the implementation of the principle of a sound economy will allow us to achieve the following: [2]:

- Complete elimination of legal barriers to the creation of new technologies in the process of creating a new non-regulatory framework;
- Closing and developing the infrastructure of a smart economy, including the development of a system for finding and processing information, technical and logistical support in line with modern requirements;
- Ensuring the comprehensive development and modernization of the education system;
- Thorough implementation of the development of large companies, firms, state-owned enterprises and businesses in the country;
- The emergence of many organizations in the context of a rational economy.

The direction of the development of a rational economy should serve to achieve the following goals [3]:

To close the ecosystem of the Uzbek economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan;

- to close the institutional and informational gaps of the system of the country's economy;
- to carry out a baptismal change with a view to creating an information society that embraces the development of the republic;
- To increase the competitiveness of our republic on a global scale and in the global market.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 19, 2018 "On further development of information and communication technologies", July 3, 2018 "On further development of the economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan" As a result of this campaign, the electronic document flow has been closed, e-payment is being developed, and the non-regulatory framework in e-commerce is being improved.

In general, an innovative economy based on knowledge can be seen as a logical continuation of digitization. This is because the digital economy is also characterized by a significant reduction in the life cycle of innovations [4]. It is therefore expedient to dwell on the essence of innovation.

"Innovation is a set of innovations, inventions, discoveries, ideas and new approaches in the form of intellectual property, created on the basis of experience, applied to production, and at the same time bringing economic and social benefits" [5] If an innovative idea is created, Innovation is not hijab unless it is applied to production, if it proves its economic usefulness. Created innovations can be considered as innovations only when they are commercialized, put into practice and given socio-economic benefits.

According to this definition, innovation does not consist of ideas, developments, discoveries, but incorporates a completely new innovative approach and principles in the organizational-managerial description of the organization, management and efficient implementation of production facilities that serve the overall development of innovation.

Research methodology.

The methods of comparative analysis, grouping, scientific abstraction, monographic observation were used as research methodology.

Analysis and results.

Today, the lack of competitive national products in the global technology market, as well as the diversification and rectification processes in the canoe industry, are also serious problems in innovation management. Paying attention to the following figure (Figure 1), we can see that the authors of innovative developments, discoveries, inventions, created in our country for the registration of products in the prescribed manner, are submitted to the competent authority in the form of an application. Upon receipt of a positive conclusion from the competent State expert, patents are formalized by the competent state body and registered in a single rector.

3-picture. The proposed system of creation, patenting and commercialization of innovations

The results of the analysis show that the shortcomings of the current system are as follows:

- Cubs that create innovative products, that is, developers, inventions, industrial designs and utility models are created at their own expense in the absence of any financial support or privileges from the state to the authors;
- another patent fee must be paid for the registration of the created intellectual property;

The authorized body of the state for the development of innovations receives the application and passes the State examination. If the expert concludes positively, he / she will grant a patent by his / her decision, and if it is positive, he / she will return the application to the author.

A serious shortcoming of the current system and the problem is that the competent state body is limited to a formal function, such as the receipt of applications and the organization of its examination. Innovation, innovative products are created, but its future destiny, emac there is a system of organizing work on commercialization. There is currently no monitoring of innovations and their application in production, no measures have been developed and there is a significant gap between the science and the production medium

The analysis shows that we will not be able to achieve significant results in this area if we do not implement a system of creating, formalizing and commercializing developments. Of course, the following articles are of special importance in the implementation of inventions, that is, their transformation into innovations and their management:

Based on the principle that the acoci of innovation development is intellectual property, patenting of innovative ideas, improvement of the system of protection of intellectual property as one of the priorities of the Intellectual Property Agency;

to maintain a single register of issued patents for innovative ideas, developments and to establish an independent state body to monitor their implementation in order to increase innovation activity;

Individuals who have received patents in the field of innovative developments, as well as scientific works, articles and scientific papers on innovative development in the event of copyright infringement, to determine the functions and responsibilities of the competent authorities on the issue of compensation and damages.

In general, in today's world, the kiss of a smart economy is gaining momentum. In our country, certain work is being done to develop the industry. Undoubtedly, streamlining the economic sector will reduce the costs associated with product development and service delivery, improve product quality, increase volume and competitiveness, and save time. At present, in Uzbekistan, high-tech technologies are widely used in the banking system, retail cavdo, tpancpopt, energy, education, health and other areas.

Conclusions and suggestions.

Based on the above, the following conclusions and propositions have been formed:

- A smart economy is a system of economic, social and cultural communication using smart technologies, which can be, first of all, online services, online education, e-payment, and the Internet of Things.
- It is necessary to close and close the automated system of development, service multiplication and management in Japan, to modernize the economy, to develop the ICT industry. This Japanese, in turn, manifests itself as the vocitaci of bapham bepish to the yashipin economy. This is because, firstly, all the operations performed are recorded electronically, and secondly, all the information is transparent. In addition, the use of new IT in development will reduce the cost of products and services and increase competitiveness. As long as our economy is not competitive and the laws of the market are not fully implemented, the results of the ongoing economic reforms will not be impressive.
- In Japan, the increase in inconvenience in the service of the population. This, in turn, has a positive effect on the quality and well-being of the population, ensuring a significant reduction in bipolar disorder, paperwork and corruption.
- The creation of innovations, the implementation of the proposed system of patenting and their commercialization, the simplification of the patenting process can contribute to a positive solution to the problems of implementation of innovations in practice.

The implementation of the above conclusions and recommend ations will simplify the process of digitalization of intellectual property, accelerate the transformation of knowledge-based innovation development into digitalization.

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